

ABSTRACTS

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Dr. M.R. Dinesh
Director,
ICAR-IIHR,
Hesaraghatta Lake Post,
Bengaluru 560089
Karnataka, India
director@ihr.res.in
Website: www.ihr.res.in

&
President,
Society for Promotion of Horticulture,
Bengaluru, Karnataka, India
Website: www.sphindia.org
sph@ihr.res.in

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भा.कृ.अनु.प.-भारतीय बागवानी अनुसंधान संस्थान
हेस्सरघट्टा लेक पोस्ट, बेंगलूरु - 560089

ICAR- Indian Institute of Horticultural Research
Hesaraghatta Lake Post, Bengaluru - 560 089

Host Plant Resistance Study in Indian Cherry (*Cordia myxa* L.) against *Dictyla cheriani* Drake (Hemiptera: Tingidae) in Arid Region of Rajasthan

Shravan M. Haldhar

ICAR-Central Institute for Arid Horticulture, ICAR, Bikaner, Rajasthan, India

E-mail: haldhar80@gmail.com

Twenty two germplasm accessions of *Cordia myxa* were collected from Rajasthan and established at the field gene bank for the study with regards to conservation, evaluation and resistance. The study was conducted to identify resistant accessions of Indian cherry and its association with morphometric and biochemical traits. Based on Kaiser Normalization method, the germplasm accessions of *Cordia myxa* categorised as AHCM-22-1, AHCM-25 and AHCM-34 were found to be resistant; AHCM-14, AHCM-30, AHCM-31, AHCM-03 and AHCM-11 were found moderately resistant; whereas AHCM-16, AHCM-09, AHCM-29 and AHCM-04 were found to be moderately susceptible; AHCM-33, AHCM-08 AHCM-07 and AHCM-06 susceptible and AHCM-01, AHCM-26, AHCM-24 and AHCM-32 highly susceptible germplasm accessions. The per cent leaf infestation was the highest in AHCM-32 (68.51 %) and the lowest in AHCM-22-1 (12.26 %) followed by AHMM/BR-8 (14.11 %). The leaf infestations ranged from 12.26 to 68.51 % and were significantly lower in resistant germplasm accession and higher in susceptible germplasm accession. The significant positive correlation ($r = 0.965$) was observed between per cent leaf infestation and tingid bug population per leaf. Free amino acid had positive correlation with percent leaf infestation ($r=0.955$) and was found the lowest in the resistant accession and the highest in the susceptible accession, whereas phenols ($r= -0.865$), tannin ($r= -0.942$), total alkaloids ($r= -0.976$) and flavonoid ($r= -0.982$) contents had significant negative correlation with percent leaf infestation and the highest in resistance and the lowest in susceptible accession. The percent leaf infestation had significant negative correlation with length of leaf ($r= -0.868$) and width of leaf ($r= -0.835$). Leaf size, leaf roughness and leaf hairyness were found large, high rough and high hairy, respectively in resistant accession of Indian cherry. The one principal component (PCs) was extracted explaining cumulative variation of 90.07% in tingid bug infestation. The flavonoid, total alkaloid, tannins, phenols content, leaf length, width, roughness and hairiness were the novel antibiosis and antixenotic characters found in Indian cherry which were resistant to *D. cheriani*.